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Closed-loop coupling of a dynamic wake model with a wind inflow estimator

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Abstract. The estimation of turbine flow evolution provided by low-fidelity dynamic wake models, such as FLORIDyn, can be improved by the introduction of a Kalman filter based on power production measurements. However, it is not possible to infer any information about which side of an impinged rotor is affected by the wake only by the observed power, being itself a single scalar quantity. In this paper, a new closed-loop formulation of the FLORIDyn model is investigated: wind speed estimates, given by a blade load-based wind observer, are implemented into a Kalman Filter, providing information about the position of the wake over the rotor plane. The FLORIDyn model augmented with the wind flow estimator is tested in a layout of two aligned turbines and compared to a corresponding CFD simulation. The results of the proposed approach show an improved ability to predict wind flow quantities and the wake centerline position compared to the open-loop version of the model.

1. Introduction

Dynamic wake models like FLORIDyn (FLOW Redirection and Induction Dynamics) provide a dynamic description of the wake flow regime at low computational cost [10]. Thus, they could present a suitable solution for wind farm control applications [5]. Dynamic wake models consider the delay in the propagation of the flow and the fluctuations of the wake through the propagation of observation points (OPs) downstream of the wind turbine rotor in a state space description. However, due to the low-fidelity nature of the model, not all the relevant features of flow dynamics can be captured. Therefore, some errors inevitably remain in power and flow properties predictions. The state-space description lends itself to the integration of a Kalman filter, which uses measurements to correct the model online [2]. Reference [6] investigated a non-aligned two-turbine wake situation where the power production of the waked turbine was used as input to the filter. Corrections were made to the advected background wind speed as well as to the position of the impinging wake. It was shown that this closed-loop setup, based solely on power production measurements, was able to improve the estimation of a dynamic wake model and make physical corrections to the position of the wake on the impinged turbines. However, the investigated case was a partial wake interaction, with constant impingement on one side of the rotor. In reality, the observed power itself, being a single scalar quantity, cannot provide any information about which side of the impinged rotor is affected by the wake. Additional information about the inflow might be inferred using a wake-affected turbine as a sensor: the wind observer model, developed by [4], can provide wind speed estimates over different regions of the rotor area from root bending moment measurements. The methodology was deployed

in field tests as a wake detector and showed the ability of tracking the wake position over the rotor of an impinged turbine [19]. This paper proposes a further generalization of the model introduced by [6] using the additional inflow quantities provided by the observer: a Kalman filter is implemented with wind velocity measurements provided by the wind observer, to correct the predictions of a dynamic wake model. The new closed-loop formulation, augmented with the wake detector, is tested in a simulation layout of two aligned turbines under full wake conditions. A high-fidelity CFD simulation [7, 22, 23] provides the ground truth for the flow field evaluation. The results of the proposed approach are analyzed in the paper, showing a better prediction of wind flow quantities and the wake centerline position compared to the open loop configuration of the model.

2. Simulation setup

The CFD data was generated using a modified version of SOWFA (Simulator fOr Wind Farm Applications) [7, 22, 23]. Within this incompressible simulation tool, the CFD environment is directly coupled with the aeroelastic simulator FAST [16] using the actuator line method (ALM) [17, 20] for modeling the blades. The velocity-pressure coupling in the Navier-Stokes equations is solved using the PISO algorithm [12]. Turbulence is modeled using the large-eddy simulations (LES) approach, with the constant Smagorinsky method [18] being employed for modeling subgrid scales. The simulation setup consists of two IEA 3.4 MW turbines [3]. These onshore reference turbines have a hub height of 110 m and a rotor diameter D of 130 m. Nacelle and tower are fully resolved using the *snappyHexMesh* utility [11]. The turbines $T1$ and $T2$ are fully aligned in a streamwise direction, spaced $6D$ apart, with $T1$ located $4D$ from the inlet. The domain of size $2864 \times 992 \times 608 \text{ m}^3$ is discretized using a Cartesian grid with five refinement layers, where the cubic cells in the finest layer have an edge length of 1 m. The inflow was generated using the synthetic turbulence generator TurbSim [13]. It is characterized by an average free stream velocity of 7.7 ms^{-1} , a turbulence intensity of 12 % at hub height, and a shear of 0.2. The simulation time is equal to 654 s. A tracking algorithm is used to identify the location of the wake of the upstream turbine upon impingement. The method follows the proposal of [21], where a two-dimensional Gaussian distribution is used to approximate the wake deficit in a cross-sectional plane. In the present study, a Z - Y plane was placed $0.5D$ upstream of the waked turbine, as reported in Figure 1a. The tracking algorithm includes as free parameters firstly the wake width. Secondly, the offsets of the wake center from the origin in the lateral y -direction μ_{cy} , and from hub height in the vertical z -direction μ_{cz} . Figure 1b shows the streamwise velocity at the plane for the same time step as panel a. The effect of vertical shear was removed with the average flow shear. The plot additionally outlines the second turbine that is in reality located behind the plane (in the streamwise direction). The wake location was determined by fitting the Gaussian profile onto the flow slice, depicted as contour lines. To increase the robustness, the flow field was first filtered by a 5 s centered moving average filter. The wake position was thus identified for every time step of the simulation. It can be seen, that at this point in time, the instantaneous wake is displaced in negative y -direction.

A statistical evaluation of the computed wake position station reveals that the wake meanders in the lateral as well as in the vertical directions. The standard deviations of the position in lateral direction $\text{std}(\mu_{cy}) = 0.35D$ is however larger than in the vertical $\text{std}(\mu_{cz}) = 0.18D$. The ground probably has a restraining effect on the wake in the vertical direction at this separation distance [15]. The correlation of wake offset and power output of the downstream turbine is defined as $r_{c,P} = \text{cov}(\mu_c, P) / (\text{std}(\mu_c) \text{std}(P))$. In the lateral direction, there is a clear linkage with $r_{cy,P} = 0.63$. On the other hand, in the vertical direction, there is no clear correlation as $r_{cz,P} = -0.2$. This result is probably affected by phases where the wake had large lateral offsets (higher power) but was close to hub height in the vertical direction, as well as the short simulation time. As the dynamic wake model currently does not include vertical meandering

Figure 1. (a) Streamwise velocity at hub height after 360 s. The dashed line represents the location of the vertical plane. (b) Streamwise velocity at the vertical plane 0.5 D in front of the second turbine. The shaded area represents the outline and the four rotor sectors of the second turbine.

motions, only the horizontal offsets are considered in the following.

3. Methodology

3.1. Wind observer

The local wind estimations are performed using the blade loads approach developed in [4], referred to as "observer" here. The model returns an estimated value of the blade-effective wind speed (BEWS) on the rotor plane, at the generic azimuth position ψ of the blade, through the interpolation of pre-compiled look-up tables (LUTs)

$$BEWS = LUT \left(m_i, \beta, \Omega, \psi, \frac{\rho}{\rho_{ref}} \right), \quad (1)$$

using the measured out-of-plane blade root bending moment m_i , the blade pitch angle β , the rotor speed Ω and the air density ρ with ρ_{ref} as the reference air density. The LUTs were pre-computed generating a dataset from the output of standalone OpenFAST simulations [14] in a range of operative conditions of interest for the IEA 3.4 MW reference turbine [3].

Dividing the rotor into four sectors, it is subsequently possible, through a time average of the instantaneous BEWS, to compute an average value of the wind flow velocity blowing over each single sector, named sector-effective wind speed (SEWS) [4, 19]. The sectors are illustrated in Figure 1b. The trends of the SEWSs provide information regarding which side of the rotor has been impinged by the wake [4, 19]: for example, a decrease in the left SEWS compared to the right one is correlated with the positioning of the wake centerline over the left side of the turbine at a given instant. Streamwise velocities were extracted from the LES simulation at the vertical Z-Y plane placed 0.5 D in front of the waked turbine T2 reported in Figure 1a. The spatial averages of the velocities, sampled at points of the plane having the same Z-Y coordinates of the four sectors at the rotor, are considered as a benchmark to evaluate the observer predictions. Overall, the plots from Figure 2 and the values reported in Table 3.1 show a good agreement between the predicted SEWS and the averaged velocities extracted from the CFD simulation. The discrepancies between the two trends are probably due to the different definitions of the wind speeds. As mentioned, the observer outputs refer to the resulting time average of the BEWS "sensed" by the blades over each sector. On the other hand, the reference velocities represent the spatial means of the streamwise wind speed computed at each time step of the simulation. A time delay of approximately 10 seconds between the two trends is also visible from Figure 2, which is directly related to the propagation of the flow from the upstream plane

at $0.5 D$ ahead of $T2$. As reported in the previous section, the dynamic wake model FLORIDyn currently does not include vertical meandering motions, therefore only the horizontal offsets relative to the left and right sectors are considered in the following.

Figure 2. Time series of the SEWSs computed by the observer for the four sectors (U_L^{obs} , U_R^{obs} , U_{UP}^{obs} , U_D^{obs}) of the waked turbine $T2$, compared with the spatial average of the streamwise velocity corresponding to each sector (U_L^{LES} , U_R^{LES} , U_{UP}^{LES} , U_D^{LES}), extracted from a vertical plane at an upstream distance of $0.5 D$ from the rotor plane in the LES simulation. The subscripts L , R , UP and D refer to the left, right, up, and down sectors respectively, and the exponents obs and LES refer to the "observed" and the "sampled" velocities at the vertical Z - Y plane.

SECTOR	RMS [ms^{-1}]	r [-]
UP	1.03	0.96
LEFT	0.63	0.97
RIGHT	0.79	0.96
DOWN	0.98	0.97

Table 1. Root-mean-squared error and Pearson correlation coefficient r between the velocities predicted by the observer (U_L^{obs} , U_R^{obs} , U_{UP}^{obs} , U_D^{obs}) and the corresponding ones sampled from the vertical Z - Y plane upstream of $T2$ (U_L^{LES} , U_R^{LES} , U_{UP}^{LES} , U_D^{LES}). A time shift of 10 s has been applied to the velocities extracted from the SOWFA simulation to take into account the delay in the inflow propagation.

3.2. Dynamic wake model

In the following section, an overview of the main characteristics of the dynamic wake model is provided. The reader is referred to [5], [9], [10] for its exhaustive derivation. As mentioned,

the dynamic wake model FLORIDyn describes the evolution of flow quantities through the propagation of observation points (OPs) in a state-space framework. The step-wise advancement in time of the OPs models the wake movements and the delay in ambient flow changes. A conventional wake model provides the velocity deficit at the discretized positions. In the formulation of the dynamic wake model used for this study, the evolution of the wind field is described by the superposition of two different sets of OPs [5]: Wake OPs contain flow quantities associated with the individual wake of a turbine, indicated with the subscript "w". Ambient OPs represent quantities of the background flow, indicated with "amb". This separation allows for a distinct propagation speed of the two flow regimes. A number of N_w wake OPs define the wake centerline with locations $\mathbf{x}_w^k, \mathbf{y}_w^k \in \mathbb{R}^{N_w \times 1}$ in the X - Y space. The wake deficit magnitude and profile are calculated with the Gaussian wake model at every position [1]. For the generic turbine T , the wake OPs model the downstream advection process through the following system of equations in the state-space form at time k

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_w \\ \mathbf{y}_w \end{bmatrix}_T^k = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{A} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_w \\ \mathbf{y}_w \end{bmatrix}_T^{k-1} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{B} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_T \\ y_T \end{bmatrix} + \Delta t \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{A} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_w \\ \mathbf{V}_w \end{bmatrix}_T^{k-1}, \quad (2)$$

where the time step is noted Δt and the turbine position coordinates are x_T, y_T . The wake velocities $\mathbf{U}_w, \mathbf{V}_w \in \mathbb{R}^{N_w \times 1}$ represent the effective x, y -transport velocities of the wake. These velocities are slower than the free stream wind speed as they are reduced by the average velocity deficit $\Delta \mathbf{U}$ at each OP. Matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} are defined as in the original study [9]: \mathbf{A} has a lower diagonal form, propagating states to the next OP, while the input matrix \mathbf{B} allows new states to enter the system at the first OP. A depiction of the model is shown in Figure 3b.

Secondly, a number N_{amb} of ambient OPs (black points) with locations $\mathbf{x}_{amb}^k, \mathbf{y}_{amb}^k \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{amb} \times 1}$ represent the undisturbed background field, originating similarly at every turbine. These OPs contain the ambient wind speed and turbulence intensity $\mathbf{U}_{amb}^k, \mathbf{V}_{amb}^k, \mathbf{I}_{amb}^k \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{amb} \times 1}$, which are propagated to the next OP with

$$\mathbf{F}_{amb}^k = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{F}_{amb}^{k-1} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{F}_{amb,1}^k, \quad (3)$$

where F represents a generic ambient quantity (velocity component or turbulence intensity). The locations of the ambient OPs are updated in the same manner as the wake OPs, according to (3.2), albeit using the undisturbed wind speeds $\mathbf{U}_{amb}, \mathbf{V}_{amb}$, instead of $\mathbf{U}_w, \mathbf{V}_w$. The conditions from ambient OPs are transferred to the wake regime, at every iteration by linear interpolation based on distance. Upon impingement at the second turbine, the background flow quantities from external ambient OPs are transferred to the waked turbine by an inverse distance weighting, which can be written as $\mathbf{F}_{amb,ext} \rightarrow \mathbf{F}_{amb,1}$. Subsequently, the effective impinging velocity deficit is mapped to the respective rotor disk through spatial interpolation, i.e. $\Delta \mathbf{U}_{ext} \rightarrow \Delta \mathbf{U}_1$. This allows the calculation of the effective sector equivalent wind speeds at the rotor. New ambient conditions and control inputs enter the state space at the first OP located at the turbine rotor. For the free stream turbine, the ambient conditions of wind speed and direction are sampled from the CFD flow field.

3.3. Kalman filter for the dynamic wake model

The following section describes the integration of the dynamic wake model with the flow observer. Figure 3a gives an overview of the system, with the main elements highlighted. In this study, the LES simulation is tasked with representing the real flow field and turbine behavior. The dynamic wake model is fed by sampled flow quantities that represent available measurements at a full-scale turbine, like wind direction from the nacelle wind vane. The more detailed rotor inflow measurements of the observer are used to correct the model estimate.

Figure 3. (a) Flow chart of the dynamic model and Kalman filter correction. (b) Depiction of the dynamic model after a wake position correction.

The Kalman filter is implemented in an ensemble form (enKF) [2, 6]. The focus of the present study is on the simultaneous correction of the estimates provided by the state space model of fluctuations of the ambient wind speed U_{amb} , as well as lateral meandering motions of the wake position y_w . Accordingly, the state space vector used in the following Kalman filter equations can be a subset of the full system state, containing only these two state variables. For the first turbine, this is expressed as

$$\mathbf{x}_{T1}^k = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y}_w \\ \mathbf{U}_{amb} \end{bmatrix}_{T1}^k, \tag{4}$$

with the full state vector $\mathbf{x}^k = [\mathbf{x}_{T1}^k, \mathbf{x}_{T2}^k]^T$. In the enKF implementation, the process stochastics are represented by generating a number of model instantiations, corresponding to perturbed state variables. The ensemble \mathbf{X} consists therefore of N_{en} state vectors \mathbf{x}

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} | & | & | & \dots & | \\ \mathbf{x}_1 & \mathbf{x}_2 & \mathbf{x}_3 & \dots & \mathbf{x}_{N_{en}} \\ | & | & | & \dots & | \end{bmatrix}. \tag{5}$$

The system covariance matrix is the sample covariance of the state vectors, i.e. $\mathbf{P} = \text{cov}(\mathbf{X})$. The whole ensemble is advanced in time as

$$\mathbf{X}^k = f(\mathbf{X}^{k-1}, \mathbf{u}^k) , \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{u} are new flow quantities and turbine control states entering the system at the first OPs. For a simpler notation, superscript k is dropped from the following description of one Kalman filter iteration. The inclusion of process noise is performed by perturbing each ensemble member. Noise is assumed to be normally distributed, i.e. $\mathbf{w} = \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{Q})$, where $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_S \times N_S}$ is the noise covariance matrix, and N_S is the number of system states. Physically, the turbulent flow field between two turbines, which is responsible for disturbing the wake path, consists of spatially correlated fluctuations. Therefore, the current study assumes that process noise retains some correlation over distance, modeled by an exponential function [6].

The following correction step introduces measurements from the real system. The flow observer provides the effective wind speed at the left and right rotor sectors. The measurement for turbine T is consequently expressed as

$$\mathbf{z}_T = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_L^{obs} \\ \mathbf{U}_R^{obs} \end{bmatrix}_T . \quad (7)$$

The measurements $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\text{meas}} \times 1}$ need to be additionally perturbed with measurement noise $\mathbf{v} = \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{R})$, where \mathbf{R} is the measurement uncertainty matrix, to form an ensemble of observations $\mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\text{meas}} \times N_{\text{en}}}$ [8].

The equivalent system output

$$\mathbf{y}_T = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_L^m \\ \mathbf{U}_R^m \end{bmatrix}_T , \quad (8)$$

where the superscript m stands for "model", and consists of the modeled left and right sector wind speeds. For the whole ensemble, the output can be expressed by the nonlinear function $\mathbf{Y} = h(\mathbf{X})$. The system states are then connected to the system outputs through the ensemble statistics [2]. The state-to-output covariance matrix $\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}}$ as well as the output covariance matrix $\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{Y}}$ are defined as in [2, 6]. Finally, the Kalman gains are calculated according to

$$\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}} (\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{Y}} + \mathbf{R})^{-1} , \quad (9)$$

which allows for updating the system state vector as

$$\mathbf{X}^* = \mathbf{X} + \mathbf{K} (\mathbf{Z} - \mathbf{Y}) . \quad (10)$$

Figure 3b shows a schematic correction of the wake position.

4. Results

The result section compares the model in conventional open loop configuration versus the closed loop version with an activated Kalman filter. The dynamic wake model was run with a timestep $\Delta t = 5$ s. $N_w = N_{amb} = 30$ wake and ambient observation points resolve the wake and ambient flow. As mentioned, the input feed of environmental conditions to the dynamic model is sampled from the CFD simulation at the upstream turbine to resemble measurements, that would be available at a full-scale turbine. The ambient wind speed U_{amb} is obtained through the power production of the upstream turbine, the wind direction Γ from a single point 0.5 D upstream of the turbine. The upstream location was chosen over the possibility of sampling the flow at the top of the nacelle, at the normal installation point of a wind vane. This approach

Figure 4. Inflow velocity at the left (a) and right (b) sector of the downstream wind turbine.

would have necessitated corrections for flow distortions induced by the rotating machine and its wake. Additionally, a precise solution of the flow field around the nacelle would have required a finer meshing of the area, increasing the computational cost. After 100 s of simulation time, the Kalman filter was activated with an ensemble size of $N_{en} = 100$. The elements of the Q and R matrix were tuned offline for a better performance of the filter to $\sigma_{U_{amb}} = 0.2 \text{ ms}^{-1}$, $\sigma_y = 4.3 \text{ m}$ and $\sigma_{U,L} = \sigma_{U,R} = 0.5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$, respectively.

The two panels of Figure 4 show the modeled and observer-measured left and right sector wind speed. While the open loop model can follow the larger trends, it is clear, that the closed loop model shows a much better agreement, as the sector wind speeds were the target quantities of the filter. The remaining discrepancies can, on one hand, be accounted for by the natural lag time of the filter. Corrections are constantly advected downstream through equations (3.2) and (3) and leave the system, while new uncorrected states approach the turbine. Secondly, the real wake shape is at times torn apart, so it does not resemble the wake model Gaussian shape. Therefore, the filter cannot always match both sector wind speeds simultaneously. The plot additionally shows the modeled background wind speed as well as the modeled wake loss for the closed loop system. At $t = 550 \text{ s}$, the wake loss reduces to a very small value on the left side of the rotor. This is because the model predicts a large wake offset to the right side (in negative y -direction) and therefore the left side experiences an almost clean (unwaked) inflow.

As mentioned before, the wake position is used to verify if the applied corrections are physical. Figure 5 reports the lateral position of the wake at the waked turbine over the simulation time. The measurement position is estimated by the wake tracking algorithm (section 2). It can be seen that the meandering wake center crosses the rotor several times, creating partial overlap conditions. This movement causes, together with further ambient turbulence, the fluctuations and differences in the sector wind speeds, as shown in Figure 4. The plane for wake position tracking is located $0.5 D$ upstream of the rotor. To compensate the time delay, the measured curve was shifted in time by the assumed advection time of $\mathbf{U}_w/D = 10 \text{ s}$ (section 3.1).

In the open loop configuration, the wake position is a result of the past input of environmental conditions at the upstream turbine and the advection process. The plots reported in Figure 5

Figure 5. Lateral wake center position obtained from the tracking algorithm as well as estimated by the dynamic wake model.

show that the wake movements in the order of 100 s or larger than $0.5 D$ are indeed captured by the open loop model. However, the corrected model with Kalman filter is able to show an improved agreement on the smaller fluctuations. A larger discrepancy starting at 450 s is probably connected to a movement in the downward direction of the wake. This can be at the moment not captured and likely prevents a better correction here. As suspected in the previous figure, towards the end of the simulation, the wake is displaced in negative y -direction. At this point, both models show a higher discrepancy in the measurement. Observability is lost, as the wake does hardly impinge on the turbine at this point in time. This can be also seen in Figure 4 where the sector wind speeds have almost the same value at $t = 600$ s. Overall, the r.m.s. - error on the total rotor inflow velocity is reduced from 0.63 ms^{-1} to 0.35 ms^{-1} .

5. Concluding remarks

In this paper, a new closed-loop formulation of the FLORIDyn model is presented and compared to a SOWFA simulation. Wind speed estimates from a load-based flow observer are implemented into an ensemble Kalman filter to correct the predictions of the model in terms of background flow velocity and position of the wake. Preliminary results show that the proposed approach is capable of better following the effects of smaller inflow fluctuations compared to the open loop configuration. The additional information about the inflow provided by the observer improves the performance of the standard FLORIDyn framework in full wake conditions, opening up interesting opportunities for wind farm control applications. Further studies are needed to evaluate the potential applicability of the model in different environmental conditions and more complex operative setups, considering the typical yaw-misaligned conditions used in wake-steering wind farm control.

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